

IoT-Gen: A DATASET GENERATED FROM REAL IoT DEVICES FOR ANALYSIS OF DoS/DDoS AND OTHER CYBER ATTACKS ON NETWORKS

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Abstract

Attackers exploit a number of vulnerabilities in Internet of Things (IoT) devices to perpetrate denial-of-service (DoS) and distributed DoS (DDoS) attacks as well as other cyber-attacks in networks. Measures to counter such attacks require availability of existing datasets that can be used to test some network security mechanisms. The 'IoT-Gen' is a new dataset generated from physical and real IoT devices for network traffic. It has 2 attack traffic captures executed in 6 IoT devices and one capture for normal IoT devices, totaling 3 packet captures (PCAP) files, which have their converted comma-separated value (CSV) files. The attack traffic was generated by simulating floods of Transport Control Protocol (TCP) and User Datagram Protocol (UDP) with Kali Linux's hping3 in the real IoT network testbed. The testbed setup includes a Raspberry Pi 4 configured as router to act as Wi-Fi access point and connects to the internet as well as Raspberry Pi 2 running on Apache Web Server for attack victim. Other testbed hosts include android phone, 3 personal laptop/desktop computers, and the real IoT devices that are connected to the Wi-Fi access point. A limitation with the IoT-Gen dataset is that it has yet to be validated using different machine learning (ML) classification algorithms and also evaluating the performance metrics. However, Python programming code has been developed for calculating and visualizing the correlations of the IoT-Gen dataset features, resulting in Pearson Correlation Matrix table and Heatmap. The correlation approach is the standout difference when comparing the IoT-Gen to other datasets reviewed in the paper. The goal of the IoT-Gen dataset, which is publicly available, is to offer a large attack dataset from physical and real IoT devices traffic and IoT normal traffic for researchers to use to analyze DoS/DDoS and other cyber-attacks on IoT networks over the Internet.

Keywords: Cyber attacks, Dataset, DoS/DDoS attacks, IoT devices, IoTNetworks.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Due to the large number of devices connected to modern information and communication technology (ICT) systems networks, the volume of data exchanges through global networks that constitute the Internet are increasing yearly. The rapid expansion in connectivity of IoT devices contribute to this huge global data traffics exchanges (Ebong et al., 2025). IoT devices are physical and include consumer types such as smart TVs, smart speakers, toys, wearables etc. There are also enterprise and industrial IoT (IIoT) devices (Ferrag et al., 2022) such as smart meters and commercial security systems. Because of their web-enableness, IoT devices can be assigned internet protocol (IP) addresses, connect wirelessly to conventional networks, and able to transmit data. The connectivity, networking and communication protocols used with IoT devices depend largely on their specific applications deployment (Ebong et al., 2025). Apart from indoor deployments as in homes, offices, factories and industries, IoT devices are also deployed outdoors as with smart city technologies which include monitors for traffics and weather conditions.

IoT devices however have major concern in security and vulnerabilities that can be exploited for cyber attacks, particularly DoS and DDoS attacks (Snehi & Bhandari., 2022). Such IoT vulnerabilities include insecure web interfaces, insecure software and network services, insufficient authentication and authorisation, weak physical security, and lack of transport

encryption (Saez-de-Camara et al., 2024). Bad actors have wreaked havoc by using the numerous Internet-connected IoT devices within organisations to launch DoS/DDoS and other cyber attacks. DoS attacks also exploit weaknesses in the computer systems networks due to their technology that relate to the TCP/IP and Operating Systems(OS). Attack incidents as reported include the Amazon Web Services that was attacked by a massive DDoS in 2020 and the Russian Internet giant, Yandex, attacked by a huge DDoS in 2021 (Kumari & Jain., 2023). The financial services sector have been the most targeted for DDoS attacks and this accounted for about 25 percent of all attacks in the first quarter of 2021 (Singh & Jain., 2023). With the fast expansion and connection of IoT devices in global systems networks, it is estimated that IoT devices will reach a staggering number of 24.6 billion connected devices by 2025 (Alahmadi et al., 2023). In view of the DoS/DDoS and other cyber attacks recorded, the need for security of IoT environments and IoT systems networks, become critical for continued data transmissions through the Internet.

There are available IoT datasets for use for IoT analysis. Some are commonly used in cyber attacks scenarios including DoS/DDoS types that also support message protocol such as the Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT). The MQTT protocol is based on the TCP/IP used in IoT networks. Such datasets that focus on IoT include the IoT-23 (Garcia et al., 2020), MedBloT (Guerra-Manzanares et al.,

2020), TON_IoT (Alsaedi et al., 2020; Booiij et al., 2021), MQTTset (Vaccari et al., 2020) and DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT (Alatram et al., 2023) datasets, etc. Some of the mentioned datasets are also used to evaluate cybersecurity applications in IIoT networks and in critical infrastructures.

In this paper, IoT devices are deployable in smart enterprise offices that characterise both legitimate and attack traffics on the network. The IoT-Gen dataset defines the use of Pearson Correlation statistical measure to evaluate features of the IoT dataset and for analysis of the dataset as well. The proposed dataset, which are publicly released, can be accessed by the research community to help on the research problems related to DoS/DDoS and other cyber attacks on networks requiring IoT analysis. This justifies the aim to do this research work. The only limitation of the IoT-Gen dataset is that it has yet to be validated and the performance metrics evaluated.

The remaining of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 highlights the literature review. Section 3 reports related works on the topic and gaps in knowledge. Section 4 describes in detail the methodology for generating the IoT-Gen dataset. Section 5 presents the results obtained and discussion that followed. Section 6 concludes the paper and suggests future work on the topic.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

Networks with connected IoT devices are

vulnerable to various cyber attacks, which can be categorised broadly into two attack types, namely, network-based and physical attacks. The network-based attacks include DoS/DDoS, malware infections, man-in-the-middle (MITM) attacks, and data interception (Singh et al., 2024). Other network-based attacks include brute-force, ransomware and credential stuffing, which all exploit vulnerabilities in IoT devices. The physical attacks target the devices themselves, involving tampering with the devices to compromise security, access data, or alter the functionality.

IoT Networks

IoT networks refer to a system of interconnected IoT devices, sensors, and systems that communicate and exchange data with each other and with cloud-based services, often without human intervention. According to (Vaccari et al., 2021), IoT networks enable home automation, data analytics, and improved efficiency across various industries, critical infrastructures such as hospitals, banks, and power grid, as well as other applications.

IoT Devices and Protocols IoT is viewed as a dynamic technological revolution representing future communications and computing in many areas. It is not about a single technology but various complementary technological developments (Sasi et al., 2024). The technological forms include wireless sensors, software, actuators and radio frequency identification (RFID). Using the IoT, physical

objects can be empowered to create, receive and exchange data in a seamless manner. Additional protocols that support IoT applications are Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP), Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) and Extensible Message and Presence Protocol (XMPP) (Sasi et al., 2024). MQTT is prominent and it is a message protocol that utilizes the broker-based publish-subscribe protocol, with the publisher running over TCP. It relies on the Secure Socket Layer/Transport Layer Security (SSL/TLS) for security mechanism. There are vulnerabilities and imitations with the MQTT that may cause DoS attack. Such include disrupting the MQTT broker services,

exhausting MQTT client and broker with messages above 256 MB, TCP SYN flooding and bandwidth consumption, crafting MQTT subscribe packet and authentication data.

Cyber Attacks

Cyber-attacks on IoT networks are increasing and sophisticated. They exploit vulnerabilities in internet-connected IoT devices to gain unauthorized access, steal data, or disrupt operations. As explained in (Bobrovnikova et al., 2020), cyber-attacks can range from simple data breaches to large-scale DDoS attacks leveraging compromised IoT devices as botnets as in Fig 2.1.

Fig 2.1: General Structure of Cyber-Attack in IoT Network (Prasad et al., 2024).

DoS/DDoS Attacks

Based on the protocol level or layer of the Open System Interconnection (OSI) model targeted in conventional networks with connected IoT devices, DDoS attacks can be classified as Network/Transport and Application-levels DDoS Attacks (Anusuya et al., 2023; Clinton & Hoque., 2024). The Network/Transport-level

DDoS attacks can be launched using TCP, UDP, Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP), and Domain Name System (DNS) protocol packets (Ahmad et al., 2024). They are designed to disrupt a legitimate user's connectivity. Likewise, the Application-level DDoS attacks can be launched using the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) or DNS to disrupt the

legitimate user's services. However, the greatest threat of DDoS attacks is TCP SYN flooding. DDoS flooding attacks waste a lot of resources such as processing time and space on the paths that lead to the machine being targeted. Thus, analysing datasets from such IoT-based networks are crucial for success in mitigation.

IoT Dataset

IoT dataset refers to the data collected from various internet-connected devices and sensors within the IoT ecosystem. This data can include sensor readings, environmental information, user interactions, and device status updates. According to (Buedi et al., 2024; Sa'Idi & Jamil., 2023), IoT datasets are crucial for various applications, including ML, data analysis, features comparisons for profiling, and real-time decision-making.

3.0 RELATED WORKS

There have been publications on datasets focused on IoT devices for analysis. While some of such datasets are real and obtained from actual IoT networks as in (Almaraz-Rivera et al., 2022), others are synthetic and obtained from simulated devices and networks. Some of the datasets have been used in training and testing of detection algorithms for cyber attacks including DoS/DDoS attacks on IoT networks (Hussain et al., 2021). The quality and quantity of dataset used are important in determining the results. It is imperative the datasets include quality samples of normal (benign) and attack (malicious) traffics. Thus, capturing real-world

IoT network traffic scenarios with full PCAPs, CSV-converted files, with extracted features, is very essential. A number of IoT datasets suitable for IoT analysis as mentioned earlier in the paper are highlighted subsequently in the related works to assist in determining the methodology used in the generation of the proposed IoT-Gen dataset in the study.

IoT-23 Dataset

According to (Garcia et al., 2020), the IoT-23 is a dataset of network traffic from IoT devices. It consists 20 malware (malicious) PCAP files carried out in infected IoT devices, and 3 benign captures for real IoT devices traffic. It was published in January 2020. It is a large dataset, real and labeled IoT traffics for researchers to develop ML algorithms (Nanthiva et al., 2021). The scenarios for the sample captures included a Raspberry Pi, that used protocols such as HTTP, DNS, Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP), Telnet, SSL and Internet Relay Chat (IRC) that performed different actions. The benign scenarios were obtained by capturing the traffics of 3 real IoT devices, namely, a Philips HUE Smart LED Lamp, an Amazon Echo Home Intelligent Personal Assistant, and a Somfy Smart Door Lock, for analysis of their network behaviours. The malware captures were carried out for long periods of time due to the large size of the traffic generated by each infection. Two options exist to download the IoT-23 dataset. The first is the full download with total size of 20GB, and includes the original PCAP file. The second is the light download with total size of

8.7GB. With the labels, the dataset also describes flows related to malicious activities that include command & control (C&C), DDoS, Mirai, Okiru, and Torri etc. The labels were created in the Stratosphere Laboratory, CTU University, Czech Republic.

MedBloT Dataset

According to (Guerra-Manzanares et al., 2020), the MedBloT dataset provides a labelled behavioural IoT dataset, which includes normal and actual botnet malicious network traffic. A medium-sized IoT network infrastructure with 83 IoT devices involving Paspberry Pi was deployed at the Department of Software Science, Tallinn University of Technology, Estonia. Three (3) prominent botnet malware, namely Mirai, BashLite and Torii are deployed in real and emulated IoT devices. Also, data from botnet deployment such as infection, propagation and communication with C&C server are collected. Binary and multi-classification ML models are run on the acquired data and validated, thus demonstrating the suitability of the generated dataset for botnet Intrusion Detection System (IDS) testing (Peterson et al., 2021). By focusing on early stages of botnet deployment, the MedBloT dataset provides the opportunity to perform early detection of the threat, previous to the perpetration of an attack, being able to prevent such attacks and botnet growth. The generated IoT behavioural dataset was released publicly and available as MedBloT dataset.

TON_IoT Dataset

Highlighting the TON_IoT dataset will involve referencing two related works. Firstly, (Alsaedi et al., 2020) proposed the new IIoT based datasets, called TON_IoT, which incorporate both normal sensor measurement data and types of attacks targeting IoT/IIoT applications. These datasets were designed at the Cyber Range and IoT Labs at the University of New South Wells (UNSW) Canberra, Australia, on a realistic representation of a testbed for the industry 4.0 network. They were given label to indicate normal and attack instances, and a type to indicate attack sub-classes. The generated data were stored in log and CSV files, and 7 IoT/IIoT sensors such as weather, temperature and Modbus sensors were used to capture their telemetry data. Nine (9) types of cyber-attacks including DoS/DDoS were launched against various IoT/IIoT sensors network. The datasets were combined into a single dataset to represent real-world scenarios. Seven (7) ML algorithms were used and various evaluation metrics were used to evaluate the performance of the supervised ML methods for the purpose of intrusion detection using the proposed datasets (Rashid et al., 2024).

Secondly, (Booij et al., 2021) further provide a qualitative comparison between the ToN_IoT and other IoT network security datasets. The ToN_IoT are aimed at applications such as intrusion detection (Eren & Küçük., 2023), threat intelligence, adversarial ML, and privacy- preserving models. The ToN_IoT

heterogeneous datasets also include OS datasets of Windows 7 and 10 as well as Ubuntu 14 and 18 TLS, many virtual machines (VMs), and Network traffic datasets. The testbed architecture contains 3 layers, namely, edge/IoT, fog and cloud.

MQTTset Dataset

The work by (Vaccari et al., 2020) presented the MQTTset dataset, which is related to the MQTT protocol, widely adopted in IoT networks. The dataset was built from a network of IoT sensors of different nature such as temperature, motion sensor, humidity, door lock, light intensity, smoke, fan sensor, fan speed controller, and CO-gas, able to communicate on the network in order to simulate different contexts such as home automation, monitoring of critical infrastructures or industrial contexts. The MQTTset dataset covers a broad range of attacks, including flooding DoS, MQTT Publish flood etc. Legitimate traffic was combined with different attack/malicious traffics targeting the MQTT network. Thirty three (33) necessary features were extracted for both the legitimate and malicious cases to implement a possible detection system. In order to validate the dataset, different ML algorithms were implemented and the performance metrics were evaluated (Kamaldeep et al., 2023). This demonstrated how MQTTset can be used for a possible detection system related to the MQTT protocol.

DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT Dataset

The DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT dataset was presented in (Alatram et al., 2023) and proposed for evaluating intrusion detections in IoT networks that use MQTT. The dataset can be used by security analysts to device countermeasures to attacks in MQTT networks, and by researchers to investigate existing and develop new algorithms for the efficient processing of attack data in such networks. DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT was generated at the Edith Cowan University, Australia, using a physical IoT testbed on which actual DoS attacks were performed. A variety of physical IoT sensors collected actual data such as temperature, barometric pressure, humidity, voltage, water level, carbon monoxide level, vibration, smoke, flame, motion, touch, light, buzzer, and sound. All the sensors were digital except for the water and voltage sensors. The collected data were communicated using Raspberry Pi's (publishers) through the MQTT protocol, sending the collected data to the MQTT Broker, and subsequently to Raspberry Pi's (subscribers). The dataset generated and collected contains both normal traffic data and attack traffic data. Attacker machines created 10 Dos/DDoS scenarios against the MQTT protocol. Various algorithms were used for programming the sensors, as well as the ML classifiers (Khan et al., 2024; Batra I et al., 2024). The initial analysis was conducted using confusion matrix. The applicability of the dataset was verified via experiments based on real-world attack scenarios. The dataset contains 30 features.

Gaps in Knowledge through Attributes and Future Works in the Reviewed Literatures

Having discussed the selected IoT-focused datasets, their various attributes are highlighted at Table 3.1 for easy comparison, analysis, and access by the community of researchers in the related field. Also at Table 3.2 are the future works suggested in the reviewed literatures on the various datasets. By leveraging the future

works of these related literatures, the gaps in knowledge are adequately brought out to form the bases for the methodology in generating the IoT-Gen, the new dataset for the physical and real IoT-based network analysis for DoS/DDoS and other cyber attacks. This anchors on the use of correlation as a statistical measure to evaluate the features of the produced IoT-Gen dataset and for analysis of the dataset itself.

Table 3.1: Comparison of the IoT-Focused Datasets.

Serial	Attributes	IoT Datasets				
		IoT-23 Dataset	MedBloT Dataset	TON_IoT Dataset	MQTTset Dataset	DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT Dataset
1.	Author and Year	Garcia et al., 2020	Guerra-Manzanares et al., 2020	Alsaedi et al., 2020; Booij et al., 2021	Vaccari et al., 2020	Alatram et al., 2023
2.	Purpose of Dataset	Analysis of real network behaviour.	IDS Testing, Early stage detection.	Evaluating cybersecurity applications on IoT/IIoT networks.	Detection Sytem to protect IoT and critical infrastructures.	Evaluating Intrusion Detection (ID) in IoT Networks that use MQTT.
3.	Laboratory	Stratosphere Lab, CTU Univ, Czech.	Software Science Dept, Tallinn Univ, Estonia.	Cyber Range and IoT Labs , UNSW, Canberra, Australia.	Github Repository Organisation.	Edith Cowan Univ, Australia.
4.	Testbed Scenario, Architecture	Include Raspberry Pi	Include Raspberry Pi	3 layers -Cloud, Fog, Edge/IoT.	Smart Home Environment	Include Raspberry Pis.
5.	Size of IoT Network	Large	Medium	Large-scale	Large	Large
6.	IoT Devices	3 - Real	83 - Real and Emulated.	-	8- MQTT Sensors	Physical (mostly digital)
7.	Protocols	6	-	-	MQTT-related	MQTT-related
8.	Malicious/Attack	20 (PCAP files).	3- Botnet Malware-	9- Attack Families	Attack	Attack - DoS/DDoS - 10
9.	Benign/Normal	3	Normal	Normal	Normal	Normal Traffic
10.	Dataset Size, Stored	Full (20GB) and Light (8.7GB)	-	Log, CSV files.	PCAP, CSV files	-
11.	Labeled Data	Attack, Benign etc.	Normal, Malicious	Normal, Attack, Attack Sub-classes.	-	-
12.	Features Extracted	-	-	-	33- Legitimate and Malicious.	30
13.	ML Classification and Algorithms	-	Binary, Multi-	7 Algorithms plus LSTM for DL.	ML Algorithms used.	ML Classification
14.	Validation on Data, Evaluation Metrics	-	Validated	Performance Evaluation on Metrics	Validated, Evaluated	Confusion Matrix, Conventional Metrics
15.	Dataset Release	-	Public, Available.	-	Public, Available.	Available on request

Table3.2: Suggested Future Works by the Different Authors of the IoT-focused Datasets

Datasets, Authors/Years	IoT-23 Dataset (Garcia et al., 2020)	MedBloTDataset (Guerra-Manzanares et al., 2020)	TON_IoT Dataset (Alsaedi et al., 2020; Booij et al., 2021)	MQTTset Dataset (Vaccari et al., 2020)	DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT Dataset (Alatram et al., 2023)
Future Works	-	Aiming to overcome the scarcity of relevant data sources in IoT network security and limitations of the existing data sets.	Industry and academia to jointly start the process of defining features and attack classes to create truly heterogeneous and effective IoT network intrusion detection dataset.	Extension of the data to integrate other innovative attacks against IoT-based protocols and to add more complex data in the scenario.	<p>a. The benign traffic data could be incorporated into other attack data that is not DoS/DDoS-based.</p> <p>b. The data could be used to test other protocols than MQTT.</p>

4.0 METHODOLOGY

The methodology was evolved based on the objectives of the paper, which include the following:

- i Develop a physical environment for the real IoT medium (LAN)-based network.
- ii Generate a DoS/DDoS dataset from the real IoT LAN-based network.
- iii Capture PCAP files with Wireshark..
- iv Convert PCAP files to CSV files.

The methodology discusses the research methods, materials required and implementation of the generation of a dataset from real (physical) IoT devices for analysis of DoS/DDoS and other cyber attacks in networks. The research methods center on the flowchart of Fig 4.1 that involve setting up the physical IoT LAN network testbed by installations and configurations, launching DoS/DDoS attack

floods using TCP and UDP protocols through the physical IoT LAN network, as well as capturing the dataset in PCAP files. The research materials including applications software to set up the testbed to achieve the objectives are stated in Table 4.1.

Setting up the Physical IoT Network

The physical IoT network setup includes a Raspberry Pi 4 that acts as Wi-Fi access point and connects to the internet as well as Raspberry Pi 2 running on Apache Web Server for attack victim. Other devices include 6 physical and real IoT devices, android phone, and 3 personal laptop/desktop computers. Fig 4.2 shows the IoT LAN-internet scenario testbed with the Raspberry Pi 4 configured as router to provide the Wi-Fi access point (Meyer-Berg et al., 2020) for connecting the IoT devices and other hosts for link to the internet.

Figure 4.1: Flowchart for Configuration of the Physical

Table 4.1: Research Materials including Applications Software for Setting up the IoT Smart Enterprise Office LAN.

Materials	Type	Description	Remark
Nodes	3 x HP Laptop/Desktop Computers.	OS – Windows 10	
Network Devices	a. Wi-Fi Network – Raspberry Pi 4. b. Bluetooth.	a. Raspberry Pi 4 - Configured as Wi-Fi Access Point as Router. b. Bluetooth - Connect IoT devices to Android phone connected to Wi-Fi network.	
Network Tools	a. Kali Linux VM. b. Raspberry Pi 2. c. Wireshark.	a. Kali Linux VM - Running on ORACLE on desktop at DoS source. b. Raspberry Pi 2 - Running on Apache Web Server at DoS victim. c. Wireshark - Configured to record/capture large number of packets over long time period at victim desktop.	Both DoS source laptop and Victim laptop connected to Wi-Fi.
Generation of DoS Attacks	TCP and UDP floods.	TCP and UDP floods to be simulated using Kali Linux's hping3.utility tool.	
Generation of Normal Traffic	6 IoT Devices	IoT Devices- Table 4.2 and Fig 4.3 - 4.8.	
Framework Tool	a. Bash – Command-line Interpreter. b. Python and its Libraries.	a. Bash - For Installation, Configuration etc. b. Python/Libraries – Data Preprocessing, Analysis, Computing etc.	Network

Fig 4.2: Testbed for IoT LAN-Internet Setup.

I Configuration of the Raspberry Pi 4 as Router. The initial process entails configuring the Raspberry Pi 4 as router with defined Service Set Identifier (SSID) and password in order to capture the packets from the communication process of the IoT network. Steps taken earlier include ensuring administrative (local) access to the Raspberry Pi 4 as part of the installation, with screen and keyboard also connected to it. This was followed by connecting the Raspberry Pi 4 to the Ethernet network and booting its OS. Further step ensure the OS on the Raspberry Pi 4 was up to date and rebooting if packages were installed. Highlight of the processes include the following:

(1) Installing the Access Point and Network Management Software. For the Raspberry Pi 4 to work as access point, the *hostapd* access point software package was installed: `sudo apt install hostapd`. This enabled the wireless access point service and set it to start when the Raspberry Pi 4 boots: `sudo systemctl unmask hostapd: sudo systemctl enable hostapd`. In order to provide network management services such as DNS and DHCP to wireless clients, the *dnsmasq* software package was installed for the Raspberry Pi 4: `sudo apt install dnsmasq`. Then, the net filter-persistent and its plugin iptables-persistent were installed. This utility helps by saving firewall rules and restoring them when the Raspberry Pi 4 boots: `sudo`

`DEBIAN_FRONTEND=noninteractive apt install -y netfilter-persistent iptables-persistent`. The software installation was complete and software package configured.

(2) Setting up the Network Router. The Raspberry Pi 4 will run and manage a standalone wireless network. It will also route between the wireless and Ethernet networks, providing internet access to wireless clients including the real IoT devices.

(3) Defining the Wireless Interface IP Configuration. The Raspberry Pi 4 runs a DHCP server for the wireless network. This requires static IP configuration for the wireless interface (`wlan0`) in the Raspberry Pi 4. The Raspberry Pi 4 also acts as the router on the wireless network, and is given the first IP address in the network, that is `192.168.4.1`. To configure the static IP address, the configuration file for `dhcpcd` is edited: `sudo nano /etc/dhcpcd.conf`. At the end of the file is added the following: `interface wlan0: static ip_address=192.168.4.1/24: nohook wpa_supplicant`.

(4) Enabling Routing and IP Masquerading. The Raspberry Pi 4 is configured to let wireless clients access computers on the main (Ethernet) network, and from there the internet (Poisson et al., 2024). To enable routing by allowing traffic to flow from one network to the other in the Raspberry Pi 4, a file using the stated command with the contents below was created: `sudo nano /etc/sysctl.d/routed-ap.conf`: File contents: #

`https://www.raspberrypi.org/documentation/configuration/wireless/access-point-routed.md`: # Enable IPv4 routing: `net.ipv4.ip_forward=1`: Enabling routing will allow hosts from network `192.168.4.0/24` to reach the LAN and the main router towards the internet. In order to allow traffic between clients on this foreign wireless network and the internet without changing the configuration of the main router, the Raspberry Pi 4 can substitute the IP address of wireless clients with its own IP address on the LAN using a masquerade firewall rule. This process is configured by adding a single firewall rule in the Raspberry Pi 4: `sudo iptables -t nat -A POSTROUTING -o eth0 -j MASQUERADE`. Now the current firewall rules for IPv4 (including the rule above) and IPv6 is saved to be loaded at boot by the `netfilter-persistent` service: `sudo netfilter-persistent save`. Filtering rules are saved to the directory: `/etc/iptables`.

(5) Configuring the DHCP and DNS Services for the Wireless Network. The DHCP and DNS services are provided by `dnsmasq`. The default configuration file serves as a template for all possible configuration options, so the file is renamed and a new one is edited: `sudo mv /etc/dnsmasq.conf /etc/dnsmasq.conf.orig`: `sudo nano /etc/dnsmasq.conf`: The following is added to the file and saved:

```
interface=wlan0 #Listening interface
d h c p -
range=192.168.4.2,192.168.4.20,255.255.255.
0,24h
# Pool of IP addresses served via
DHCP
```

```

domain=wlan      # Local wireless
DNS domain
address=/gw.wlan/192.168.4.1
#Alias for this router

```

The Raspberry Pi 4 will deliver IP addresses between 192.168.4.2 and 192.168.4.20 to wireless DHCP clients, who should reach the Raspberry Pi 4 under the name `gw.wlan` from wireless clients.

(6) **Ensuring Wireless Operation.** The Linux OS helps users by allowing applications to be configured with a two-letter Wi-Fi country code. In the Raspberry Pi 4 OS, 5 GHz wireless networking is disabled until a Wi-Fi country code has been configured by the user, usually as part of the initial installation process.

(7) **Configuring the Access Point Software.** The `hostapd` configuration file, located at `/etc/hostapd/hostapd.conf` is created, to add the various parameters for the new wireless network: `sudo nano /etc/hostapd/hostapd.conf`: Such parameters include channel, network name, password.

```

country_code=Ng
interface=wlan0
ssid=Pi4Net
hw_mode=g
channel=7
macaddr_acl=0
auth_algs=1
ignore_broadcast_ssid=0
wpa=2
wpa_passphrase=12345678900
wpa_key_mgmt=WPA-PSK

```

```

wpa_pairwise=TKIP
rsn_pairwise=CCMP

```

The line `country_code=Ng`, configures the computer to use the correct wireless frequencies in Nigeria. To use the 5 GHz band, the operations mode can be changed from `hw_mode=g` to `hw_mode=a`. Possible values for `hw_mode` is:

```

a = IEEE 802.11a (5 GHz) (Raspberry Pi 3B+ onwards)
b = IEEE 802.11b (2.4 GHz)
g = IEEE 802.11g (2.4 GHz)

```

(8) **Running the New Wireless Access Point.** By restarting the Raspberry Pi 4, it can be verified that the wireless access point has become automatically available: `sudo systemctl reboot`. Once the Raspberry Pi 4 has restarted, the wireless networks with the wireless clients can be searched for. The network SSID specified in file `/etc/hostapd/hostapd.conf` would now be present, and it would be accessible with the specified password.

ii **Installing and Running the Apache Server on the Raspberry Pi 2.** This can be achieved by turning on the Pi 2 and logging onto it with the virtual network computing (VNC) server software installed on any of the hosts on the physical network. The configured IP address of the Pi 2 is 192.168.4.2. Once logged on, the terminal of the Pi 2 is activated from the commands as follows:

(1) **Installing Apache 2.** Firstly, the available packages are updated by typing the command into the Terminal: `sudo apt update`:

Then, the Apache 2 package is installed with the command: `sudo apt install apache2 -y`:

(2) Testing the Web Server. By default, Apache puts a test Hypertext Markup Language (HTML) file in the web folder. This default web page is served when browsing `http://localhost/` on the Pi 2. To find the Pi 2 IP address, type `hostname -I` at the command line.

iii Connecting all Hosts including IoT Devices to the Router. Once the SSID of the Pi 4 starts to broadcast, all the 6 IoT devices and the hosts can connect to the network. IP addresses will be dynamically given to each host apart from the Pi 2 (victim) which is given a static IP address (192.168.4.2). This was done to ease communications with the VNC server.

iv Configuring the IoT Devices. The 6

IoT devices in Table 4.2 are made to interface with the mobile applications over the internet. This enables the metrics, that is the communication behaviours of the IoT devices, which are either periodic or random messages, to be captured unto a remote server (Al Tfailly et al., 2025). All that is required for the IoT devices to work is to download the mobile applications indicated from the Google or Apple Play Store unto a mobile phone and connect the mobile phone to the network. The configurations of the IoT devices shown in Fig 4.3- 4.8 are then done. For example, with the smart camera bulb, once the link with the application is setup, the application can transmit recorded audio and video messages (motion, picture, light etc) to the mobile phone through the Pi 4 network.

Table 4.2: Six (6) IoT Devices and their Mobile Applications.

Serial	IoT Device	Mobile Application	Manufacturer	Metrics (Behaviour)
1.	Smart Camera Bulb	iCsee	Shenzhen Shooscam	Random
2.	Smart Switch	eWeLink	Sonoff	Periodic
3.	Smart Bulb	eWeLink	Sonoff	Periodic
4.	Smart Plug	eWeLink	Sonoff	Periodic
5.	Smart Motion Detector	Tuya	Ningbo Kingdun	Random
6.	Smart Smoke Detector	Tuya	Shenzhen PST	Random

Fig 4.3: Smart Camera Bulb.

Fig 4.4: Smart Switch.

Fig 4.5: Smart Bulb.

Fig 4.6: Smart Plug.

Fig 4.7: Smart Motion Detector.

Fig 4.8: Smart Smoke Detector.

Installing Wireshark

This involves installing and running wireshark on the victim (Pi 2) while operating the 6 IoT devices and communicating between the various hosts on the Pi 4 network (Mathews et al., 2022). Login to the Pi 2 via VNC server and run the terminal. Install wireshark using the command: `sudo apt install wireshark -y`

Normal Traffic Capturing

The bash command is used to run wireshark: `Sudo wireshark`: The interface to be captured is then selected and the normal capture process starts. After a short while, the capturing is stopped and the captured file in PCAP is saved (Ghazanfar et al., 2020). The normal capture process is repeated several times while operating the IoT devices.

Attack Traffic Capturing

In this part, the host machine is run with Kali Linux and `hping3` is started from the terminal with the command:

```
sudo hping3 -V -S --flood 192.168.4.2#
for tcp flood
```

```
sudo hping3 -2 -V -S --flood
192.168.4.2#for udp flood
```

Attack traffics of TCP and UDP floods are launched. Wireshark is started to capture the attack traffic as PCAP file and recorded. This is repeated several times and the attack file is saved.

Correlation as Statistical Measure for Evaluating Features and Analysing the IoT-Gen Dataset

Correlation is one of the statistical measures that has been used to evaluate features and analysing

the produced IoT-Gen dataset. Correlation is obtained from the ratio of covariance of two variables to a product of variance (of the variables). It takes a value between +1 and -1 as attributes strength (magnitude) with a developed Python programming code (Lysenko et al., 2022). An extreme value on both the side means they are strongly correlated with each other. A value of zero indicates a nil correlation but not non-dependence. Pearson Coefficient, a widely used Correlation Coefficient (CC) was used in the work for measuring the linear relationship between the feature sets of the TCP IoT-based attack dataset. The mathematical formula to derive Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) is at Equation 4.1.

$$r = \frac{\sum_i(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_i(x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_i(y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad 4.1$$

where x = the independent variable, y = the independent variable, n = number of data points in the sample, \bar{x} = the mean of the independent variable x , \bar{y} = the mean of the dependent variable y . The idea is that the features with the lowest CC Average will introduce less ambiguity in the dataset. CC Average scores have been tabulated in order from the lowest to the highest.

5.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Analysing the PCAP and CSV Files of the IoT-Gen Dataset

The PCAP file is the standard file format used by Wireshark to store the captured IoT network traffic data. It contains the raw network packets,

allowing users to analyze and dissect communication between IoT devices. Thus, the PCAP file is used for network forensics, security analysis, and performance monitoring. The PCAP process by the Wireshark resulted in generation of the IoT-Gen datasets, comprising 3 different PCAPs and the 3 respective CSV-converted files as indicated in Table 5.1. The PCAPs consist of TCP and UDP attack traffics as well as normal traffic. The converted CSV files which are in Microsoft Excel also consist of TCP and UDP attack traffics plus normal traffic. A CSV file allows data to be easily stored, shared, imported, and exported across different software applications (Ullah, & Mahmoud, 2020). Table 5.1 also indicates the sizes and packet totals for each file of the datasets. It would be observed that the sizes of the PCAP files are greater than the sizes of their respective CSV files even though they have the same packet totals. The IoT-Gen datasets are also indicated in Table 5.2 but display further information about the datasets such as the Frame No. (or packet No.), the corresponding IP or media access control (MAC) Addresses for both Source and Destination, and the Protocol. The 7 features of the IoT-Gen dataset are Frame No., Time, Source, Destination, Protocol, Length, and Information, in that order. Fig 5.1 and Fig 5.2 show the screen snapshot copies of PCAP and CSV files respectively for the Normal Traffic LiveNet dataset. According to (Suparna, & Manjaiah, 2024), PCAPs are critical for hunting cyber-attacks, solving network outages, or tracking down performance issues in IoT networks.

Table 5.1: Dataset Types indicating Sizes and Packets.

Serial	Dataset Description	Type and File	Size	Packet Total
1.	Normal_traffic_liveNet		23,372 KB	27,558
2.	Normaltraffic-physical	Microsoft Excel – CSV	2,358 KB	27,558
3.	AttackTrafficTCP-physical	Microsoft Excel – CSV	1,344 KB	12,163
4.	RealnetworkAttack Traffic	Captured Pings – PCAP	7,851 KB	12,163
5.	AttackTrafficUDP-physical	Microsoft Excel – CSV	1,025 KB	12,120
6.	Attack_traffic_liveNet	Wireshark Capture – PCAP	9,998KB	12,120

Table 5.2: Dataset Types indicating Frames Numbers and IP or MAC Addresses.

Serial	Dataset Description	Type and File	Frame No.	IP or MAC Address		Protocol
				Source	Destination	
1.	Normal_traffic_liveNet	Wireshark Capture-PCAP	3	192.168.4.5	192.168.4.255	UDP
2.	Normaltraffic-physical	Microsoft Excel – CSV	7	192.168.4.2	192.168.4.20	VNC
3.	AttackTrafficTCP-physical	Microsoft Excel – CSV	19	fe80::1d1a:53e:75fe:d71a	fe80::89a:e0e8:78a9:6f59	TCP
4.	RealnetworkAttack Traffic	Captured Pings-PCAP	27	fe80::89a:e0e8:78a9:6f59	fe80::1d1a:53e:75fe:d71a	TCP
5.	AttackTrafficUDP-physical	Microsoft Excel – CSV	20	192.168.4.5	192.168.4.255	UDP
6.	Attack_traffic_liveNet.pcap	Wireshark Capture-PCAP	214	192.168.4.20	192.168.4.2	TCP

Fig 5.1: Screen Snapshot of the Normal Traffic LiveNet PCAP Capture.

Fig 5.2: Screen Snapshot of the Normal Traffic LiveNet CSV Capture.

Analysis of IoT-Gen Dataset Features using Pearson Correlation Coefficient

A feature will be considered ideal for the IoT-Gen dataset if its Correlation score is low enough. That would mean that the feature does not carry any redundant information that is shared with other features and that they are as unrelated with each other as possible (Hekmati et al., 2024). Graphs have been plotted to represent features.

Python Programming Code for calculating and visualizing correlations of the IoT-Gen dataset is at Fig 5.3. The calculation by Pearson Correlation Matrix is at Fig 5.4, which also shows visualisation of the correlations in the Heatmap. The heatmap shows dark red (close to +1) that indicates strong positive correlation while dark blue (close to -1) indicates strong negative correlation. Light colors (near 0) indicate weak or no correlation. Fig 5.5 further shows the correlations of the IoT-Gen dataset in tabular form.

The correlation analysis, conducted using the PCC, revealed several notable relationships among the dataset's numerical features.

i Near-perfect Positive Correlation (r

≈ 1.00). A near-perfect positive correlation ($r \approx 1.00$) between packet number (No.) and Time reflects the sequential nature of data capture, while strong positive correlations such as Protocol–Length ($r \approx 0.83$), Length–Info ($r \approx 0.74$), and Protocol–Info ($r \approx 0.63$) indicate that certain protocols transmit larger packets containing more detailed information.

ii Strong Negative Correlations.

Strong negative correlations, including Source–Protocol ($r \approx -0.64$), Source–Length ($r \approx -0.81$), and Source–Info ($r \approx -0.88$), suggest that some sources are associated with smaller control or acknowledgment packets rather than large data transfers.

iii Weak correlations.

Weak correlations such as No.–Protocol ($r \approx 0.00$) and Destination–Length ($r \approx 0.28$), show little predictive value.

From a networking perspective, these patterns highlight how Protocol choice, Packet size, and Source behavior interact, offering insights for traffic profiling, anomaly detection, intrusion detection, and feature selection in further analysis (Hossain et al., 2024; Senthilkumar et al., 2024).

```

[1]: import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder

from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
resultColumn = pd.array([])

[2]: rawData = pd.read_csv('C:/Users/HP USER/Desktop/tcp udp captures for Real Network/attackTrafficUDP.csv')
resultDF = pd.DataFrame({"Attack": [1]*len(rawData)})

[3]: def calculate_and_visualize_correlation(df, method='pearson', visualize=True, threshold=0.5):
    """Calculates and visualizes correlation, handling categorical features."""

    # 1. Handle Categorical Features:
    for col in df.select_dtypes(include=['object']).columns: # Iterate over categorical columns
        le = LabelEncoder()
        df[col] = le.fit_transform(df[col]) # Encode categorical features to numerical

    # 2. Calculate Correlation (only on numerical columns after encoding)
    numeric_df = df.select_dtypes(include=['number']) # Select only numeric columns
    if numeric_df.empty or len(numeric_df.columns) <= 1:
        print("DataFrame is empty or has only one numeric column. Correlation cannot be calculated.")
        return None

    try:
        # Calculate the correlation matrix
        correlation_matrix = numeric_df.corr(method=method)

        if visualize:
            # Mask to display only correlations above a certain threshold
            mask = np.abs(correlation_matrix) < threshold

            # Set up the figure and axes
            plt.figure(figsize=(12, 10)) # Dynamically adjusted for larger datasets
            sns.heatmap(correlation_matrix, annot=True, cmap='coolwarm', fmt=".2f", linewidths=.5,
                        mask=mask, cbar_kws={"shrink": 0.8}, vmin=-1, vmax=1)

            # Rotate labels for readability
            plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha='right')
            plt.yticks(rotation=0)

            plt.title(f"Correlation Matrix ({method.capitalize()})")
            plt.tight_layout() # Adjust layout to prevent label cutoff
            plt.show()

        return correlation_matrix

    except Exception as e:
        print(f"An error occurred: {e}")
        return None

```

Fig 5.3: Python Programming Code on Correlations of the Dataset Features.

Fig 5.4: Visualizing the Correlations for the Dataset Features in a Heatmap.

Fig 5.5: Visualising the Correlation for the Dataset Features in Tabular Form.

6.0 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a dataset called IoT-Gen was proposed for network security officials to use to analyse and develop countermeasures against DoS/DDoS and other cyber attacks in enterprise office IoT networks. The IoT-Gen was generated by simulating TCP and UDP attack floods using Kali Linux's hping3 in 6 smart, physical and real IoT devices, namely, camera bulb, switch, plug, bulb, smoke and motion detectors, in the LAN-internet testbed. The dataset also contains normal traffic data generated from the 6 IoT devices as well. The setup of the testbed includes a Raspberry Pi 4 connecting to the internet as well as Raspberry Pi 2 for attack victim. Other testbed hosts include android phone and 3 personal laptop/desktop computers. The IoT-Gen dataset consist of PCAP files from wireshark captures and the respective converted CSV files. Python code was developed for calculating and visualizing the correlations of features of the IoT-Gen dataset. The Pearson Correlation Matrix table and heatmap results could be very useful in analysis of IoT networks, traffic profiling, features selection, or in intrusion and anomaly detections. In particular, 3 out of the 7 features, namely Protocol, Length and Source were quite notable in their interactions and offering insights to the analyses. The IoT-Gen dataset is available publicly on <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/ejebongnda/iot-gen-dataset> and <https://github.com/ejebong-coder/IoT-Gen-Dataset>. Future works would likely be to classify and validate the IoT-Gen dataset with ML

algorithms and to evaluate the performance metrics.

REFERENCES

- Ahmad A. N., Raffei A. F. M., Rasak M. F. A., & Ahmad A. (2024). Distributed Denial of Service Attack Detection in IoT Networks using Deep Learning and Feature Fusion: A Review. *Mesopotamia Journal of Cybersecurity (MJCS)*, 47-70.
- Alahmadi A. A., Aljabri M., Alhaidari F., Alharthi D. J., Rayani G. E., Marghalani L. A., Alotaibi O. B., & Bajandouh S. A. (2023). DDoS Attack Detection in IoT-Based Networks using Machine Learning Models: A Survey and Research Directions. *Electronics*, 12, 3103, MDPI.
- Alatram A., Sikos L. F., Johnstone M., Szcwczyk P., & Kang J. J. (2023). DoS/DDoS-MQTT-IoT: A Dataset for Evaluating Intrusions in IoT Networks using the MQTT Protocol. *Computer Networks*, 231, Elsevier.
- Almaraz-Rivera J. G., Perez-Diaz J. A., Cantoral-Ceballos J. A., Botero J. F., & Trejo L. A. (2022). LATAM-DDoS-IoT Dataset. *IEEE Dataport*.
- Alsaedi A., Moustafa N., Tari Z., Mahmood A., & Anwar A. (2020). TON_IoT Telemetry Dataset: A New Generation Dataset of IoT and IIoT for Data-Driven Intrusion Detection Systems. *IEEE Access*, Vol. 8, 165130-165150.

- Al Tfaily F., Ghalmane Z., Termos M., Brahmia M-E-A., Jaber A., & Zghal M. (2025). Generating Realistic Cyber Security Datasets for IoT Networks with Diverse Complex Network Properties. *Proceedings of the 10th International Conference on Internet of Things, Big Data and Security (IoT BDS)*, 321-328.
- Anusuya R., Prabhu M. R., Prathima Ch., & Kumar J. R. A. (2023). Detection of TCP, UDP and ICMP DDoS Attacks in SDN using Machine Learning Approach. *Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences*, 964-971.
- Batra I., Malik A., Sharma S., & Gochhait S. (2024). Smart Traffic Management Solution Integrating Machine Learning and Internet of Things. *IEEE2024 1st International Conference on Innovative Engineering Sciences and Technological Research (ICIESTR)*, Muscat, Oman, 2024, 1-5.
- Bobrovnikova K., Martynyuk V., Lysenko S., Denysiuk D., & Gaj P (2020). Technique for IoT Cyberattacks Detection Based on DNS Traffic Analysis. *Central Europe Workshop Proceedings (CEUR-WS)*, 2629, 19.
- Booij T. M., Chiscop I., Meeuwissen E., Moustafa N., & den Hartog T. H. (2021). ToN_IoT: The Role of Heterogeneity and the Need for Standardization of Features and Attack Types in IoT Network Intrusion Datasets. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal (JIOT)*, 3085194.
- Buedi E. D., Ghorbani A. A., Dadkhah S., & Ferreira R. L. (2024). Enhancing EV Charging Station Security Using A Multi-dimensional Datasdet: CICEVSE2024. *Research Square*.
- Clinton U. B., & Hoque N. (2024). MU-IoT: A New IoT Intrusion Dataset for Network and Application Layer Attacks Analysis. *IEEE Access*, Manipur, India, Vol. 12, 166068–166092.
- Ebong E. J., John S. N., Nyitamien D. S., & Kolawole S. F. (2025). Proactive Mitigation of DDoS IoT-Related Attack using Machine Learning and Software Defined Networking Techniques. *Academy Journal of Science and Engineering (AJSC)*, 19 (2), 104-134.
- Eren K. K., & Küçük K. (2023). Improving Intrusion Detection Systems for IoT Devices using Automated Feature Generation based on ToN_IoT dataset. *IEEE 2023 8th International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (UBMK)*, Burdur, Turkiye, 276-281.
- Ferrag M. A., Friha O., Hamouda D., Maglaras L., & Janicke H. (2022). Edge-IIoTset: A New Comprehensive Realistic Cyber Security Dataset of IoT and IIoT Applications for Centralized and Federated Learning. *IEEE Access*
- Garcia S., Parmisano A., & Erquiaga M. J. (2020). IoT-23: A Labeled Dataset with Malicious and Benign IoT

- Network Traffic. (Version 1.0.0) [Data set]. *Zenodo*.
- Ghazanfar S., Hussain F., Rehman A.U., Fayyaz U.U., Shahzad F., & Shah G. A. (2020). IoT-Flock: An Open-source Framework for IoT Traffic Generation. *IEEE International Conference on Emerging Trends in Smart Technologies (ICETST)*, Karachi, Pakistan.
- Guerra-Manzanares A., Medina-Galindo J., Bahsi H., & Nomm S. (2020). MedBlot: Generation of an IoT Botnet Dataset in a Medium-sized IoT Network. In *Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Information Systems Security and Privacy (ICISSP)*, 207-218.
- Hekmati A., Zhang J., Sarkar T., Jethwa N., Grippo E., & Krishnamachari B. (2024). Correlation-Aware Neural Networks for DDoS Attack Detection in IoT Systems. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking*, Vol. 32, No. 5, 3929-3944.
- Hossain M. A., Saif S., & Islam M. S. (2024). Interpretable Machine Learning for IoT Security: Feature Selection and Explainability in Botnet Intrusion Detection using Extra Trees Classifier. *IEEE 2024 1st International Conference on Innovative Engineering Sciences and Technological Research (ICIESTR)*, Muscat, Oman, 1-6.
- Hussain F., Abbas S. G., Husnain M., Fayyaz U., Shahzad F., & Shah G. A. (2021). IoT DoS and DDoS Attack Dataset. *IEEE Dataport*.
- Kamaldeep., Malik M., & Dutta M. (2023). Feature Engineering and Machine Learning Framework for DDoS Attack Detection in the Standardized Internet of Things. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, Vol. 10, No. 10, 8658-8669.
- Khan M. Z., Bokhari M. U., & Khan T. F. (2024). "Internet of Things Security: An Experimental Analysis of Detecting Denial of Service Attacks with Machine Learning," *IEEE 2024 1st International Conference on Innovative Engineering Sciences and Technological Research (ICIESTR)*, Muscat, Oman, 1-6.
- Kumari P., & Jain A. K. (2023). A Comprehensive Study of DDoS Attacks over IoT Network and their Countermeasures. *Computers & Security, Elsevier*.
- Lysenko S., Bobrovnikova K., Kharchenko V., & Savenko O. (2022). IoT Multi-Vector Cyberattack Detection Based on Machine Learning Algorithms: Traffic Features Analysis, Experiments, and Efficiency *Algorithms*, 15, 239, MDPI.
- Mathews J., Chatterjee P., & Banik S. (2022). CoAP-DoS: An IoT Network Intrusion Data Set. *6th International Conference on Cryptography, Security and Privacy (CSP)*, IEEE Computer Society, 91-95.
- Meyer-Berg A., Egert R., Böck L., &

- Mühlhäuser M. (2020). IoT Dataset Generation Framework for Evaluating Anomaly Detection Mechanisms. *The 15th International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security (ARES)*, Virtual Event, Ireland. ACM.
- Nanthiya D., Keerthika P., Gopal S. B., Kayalvizhi S. B., Raja T., & Priya R. S. (2021). SVM Based DDoS Attack Detection in IoT Using Iot-23 Botnet Dataset. *IEEE2021 Innovations in Power and Advanced Computing Technologies (i-PACT)*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 1-7.
- Peterson J. M., Leevy J. L., & Khoshgoftaar T. M. (2021). A Review and Analysis of the Bot-IoT Dataset. *IEEE 2021 International Conference on Service-Oriented System Engineering (SOSE)*, Oxford, United Kingdom, 20-27.
- Poisson M., Carnier R.M., & Fukuda K. (2024). GothX: A Generator of Customizable, Legitimate and Malicious IoT Network Traffic. *Workshop on Cyber Security Experimentation and Test (CSET)*, Philadelphia, 3675741-3675753.
- Prasad K. S., Lydia S. E. L., Rajesh M. V., Radhika K., Ramesh J. V. N., Neelima N. & Pokuri S. R. (2024). Augmenting cybersecurity through attention based stacked autoencoder with optimization algorithm for detection and mitigation of attacks on IoT Assisted Networks. *Scientific Reports*. Nature Portfolio.
- Rashid A., Raazi S. M. K. -U. -R., & Ali S. (2024). Detection and Mitigation of DDoS Attacks on IoT Networks Using Machine Learnin. *IEEE 2024 26th International Multi-Topic Conference (INMIC)*, Karachi, Pakistan, 1-6.
- Saez-de-Camara X., Flores J. S., Arellano C., Urbietta A., & Zurutuza U. (2024). Gotham Testbed: A Reproducible IoT Testbed for Security Experiments and Dataset Generation. *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, 21, 1, 186-203.
- Sa'Idi A. S. B., & Jamil A. M. B. (2023). IoT DDoS Attack Detection System Using Machine Learning Classification Techniques. *IEEE 2023 21st Student Conference on Research and Development (SCORED)*, Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, 234-239.
- Sales M., Santos M. P., & Rego P. A. L. (2024). MQTTProvider: A Flexible MQTT Traffic Generator for the Performance Evaluation of Complex Smart Cities Scenarios. *ResearchGate*.
- Sasi T., Lashkari A. H., Lu R., Xiong P., & Iqbal S. (2024). A Comprehensive Survey on IoT Attacks: Taxonomy, Detection Mechanisms and Challenges. *Journal of Information and Intelligence*, 2, 455-513.
- Senthilkumar A., Joshika S., Santhi L., Shashidhara K S., & Charanarur P. (2024). Pearson Correlation Coefficient based Improved Least Square - Support Vector Machine for Cyber-Attack

- Detection in Internet of Things. *IEEE2024 Third International Conference on Distributed Computing and Electrical Circuits and Electronics (ICDCECE)*, Ballari, India, 1-4.
- Sibai F.N., & Sibai A. (2024). Classifying Wireless IoT ICU Traffic with Machine Learning Models. *The 21st International Conference on Mobile Systems and Pervasive Computing (MobiSPC), Procedia Computer Science, 241*, USA, 123-128.
- Singh C., & Jain A. K. (2023). Detection and Mitigation of DDoS Attacks on SDN Controller in IoT Network using Gini Impurity. *Research Square*.
- Singh K., Kumar B., Kumar S., Singh V. P., & Singh A. (2024). Mitigation of Cyber Attacks in SDN-Based IoT Systems using Machine Learning Techniques. *International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications in Engineering (IJISAE)*, 12 (8s), 482-492.
- Snehi M., & Bhandari A. (2022). IoT-based DDoS on Cyber Physical Systems: Research Challenges, Datasets and Future Prospects. *IEEE International IOT, Electronics and Mechatronics Conference (IEMTRONICS)*, Toronto, ON, Canada, 1-8.
- Suparna N., & Manjaiah D. H. (2024). A Comprehensive Study of Datasets for Research Works in IoT Networks. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive (IJSRA)*, 13(01), 2652–2662.
- Ullah I., & Mahmoud Q.H. (2020). A Scheme for Generating a Dataset for Anomalous Activity Detection. *Canadian AI, Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence (LNAI)*, 12109, Springer Nature, Switzerland, 508–520.
- Vaccari I., Chiola G., Aiello M., Mongelli M., & Cambiaso E. (2020). MQTTset, a New Dataset for Machine Learning Techniques on MQTT. *Sensors*, 20, 6578.
- Vaccari I., Narteni S., Mongelli M., Aiello M., & Cambiaso E. (2021). Perpetrate Cyber-Attacks using IoT Devices as Attack Vector: The ESP8266 Use Case. *Italian Conference on Cybersecurity (ITASEC 21), CEUR Workshop Proceedings (CEUR-WS)*.